

Influence of Intensity Balance in Vibrotactile Stimuli to the Back and Buttock on the Sense of Realism to Video Viewing

Honoka Morita¹, and Yoshihiro Tanaka^{1,2}

¹ Nagoya Institute of Technology, Nagoya, Japan
h.morita.502@stn.nitech.ac.jp

² Inamori Research Institute for Science, Kyoto, Japan
tanaka.yoshihiro@nitech.ac.jp

Abstract. There are studies to enhance tactile experiences by providing context along with vibrotactile stimuli, as past experiences might influence tactile sensation. This study designed a system that presents vibrotactile stimuli to the back and buttock in video viewing using cushion-type tactile displays, allowing for the flexible adjustment of the proportion of the intensity in the stimulation presented to the two body areas. We investigated whether there were differences in the proportion perceived as realistic among videos with different scenes. Consequently, the experimental results indicated that changing the proportion of the intensity of the vibrotactile stimuli to the back and buttock may enhance the sense of realism compared to providing the same intensity stimuli to the both areas.

Keywords: Vibrotactile stimulation · Whole body tactile presentation · Context

1 Introduction

In recent years, studies of providing vibrotactile sensations to the body in synchronization with audios and videos have been conducted to enhance the sense of realism [1][2]. Furthermore, since tactile sensation might be influenced by past experiences, there are studies to improve the experience of tactile presentation by providing context along with vibrotactile stimulation [3][4]. However, there is a problem of low versatility due to the requirement of dedicated devices to enrich experiences.

In this study, we developed a device that can arbitrarily change the proportion of the intensity of the vibrotactile stimuli to the back and buttock with a cushion-type presentation device. We can provide vibrotactile stimuli in two different directions against the body by adopting to the back and buttock. Thereby, there is a potential for a more realistic experience than presenting them in the same intensity over the entire body. In this study, we investigated whether there are differences in the proportion of the intensity of the vibrotactile stimuli to the back and buttock among different scenes in order to improve the sense of realism in video viewing.

2 System

The system assembled in this study is shown in Fig. 1 (a). The video was presented on a monitor. The audio signal was output to the audio output terminal of the PC, one for auditory and the other for tactile sensation. Headphones (QuietComfort 35, BOSE) were used for auditory sensation. For tactile sensation, an equalizer (M108S,

Fig. 1: System and experiment

MXR) was used to cut signals with high frequencies above 500 Hz for the audio output, and the signals were amplified (AP15mk2, Fostex). The signal was presented using a vibrotactile actuator (Vp408, Acouve Laboratory, Inc.), which was fixed at the center of each cushion base. Additionally, using the dedicated GUI which was made by TouchDesigner (Build 2022.33600, Derivative Inc.), we designed the system that allows to change the output proportion of two vibrotactile actuators ensuring a constant total output when manipulated by a slider.

3 Experiment

Using the system mentioned above, we investigated the proportion of the intensity of the vibrotactile stimuli in video viewing with various scenes experienced in daily life. The cushion-type device was placed on the seat and backrest of a chair, and the participants were asked to sit back against it while vibrotactile stimuli were provided. In addition, the headphones were worn. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1 (c). First, as the intensity adjustment for each participant, we determined the lower and upper limits in the intensity of the stimulation for each of the back and buttock. The upper limit was set at the intensity at which no increase in stimulation could be distinguished. The lower limit was set at the intensity against which the intensities of the detection threshold and the upper limit were 1% and 100%, respectively. The indistinguishable and detection thresholds were estimated with vibrotactile stimuli increased at a constant amount. The experiment involved randomly playing videos and allowing participants to arbitrarily change the proportion of the intensity of the vibrotactile stimuli to the back and buttock using the slider of the GUI. When the proportion was 0%, the vibrotactile actuator for the back was at maximum output and the one for the buttock was at minimum output. On the contrary, when the proportion was 100%, the actuator for the back was at minimum output and the one for the buttock was at maximum output. The sum of the output for the back and the buttocks was set to 100% in total. Participants were asked to decide the proportion perceived as realistic from 0% to 100% for each video. They were instructed to decide the proportion within 90 seconds for each video. Ten videos were prepared: watching a person playing basketball, riding a ski lift, rain, cheering with a stick balloon, a waterfall, riding a boat, a siren, a storm, sitting on a train chair, and taking a shower. These videos involve vibrations with some intensity below 500Hz. 8 naive volunteers (21-23 years old, 7 males, 1 female) participated in the experiment.

Fig. 2: Results for each video. The score was measured by the proportion of the intensity of the vibrotactile stimulus to the buttock.

4 Result and Discussion

Fig. 2 shows the results of the proportion of the intensity of the vibrotactile stimuli for each video. The Friedman test on the results showed a significant difference among the videos ($\chi^2 = 28, p = 0.00094$). Furthermore, multiple comparisons were performed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank sum test with the Bonferroni correction for each video against the 50% value. The results showed significant tendencies for the train ($V = 36, p = 0.078$) and the shower ($V = 0, p = 0.078$) scenes. Thus, it was found that there were differences in the proportion of the vibrotactile stimuli to make presenting the stimuli more realistic depending on the scene. Therefore, it seems that adjusting the proportion of the intensity for each video may enhance the sense of realism compared to equally providing vibrotactile stimuli to the entire body.

In the future work, we will compare the sense of realism between equally stimulation and stimulation with different proportions depending on the scene when providing vibrotactile stimuli to the whole body and analyze relations between the scene and the resulting proportion. Furthermore, we will physically measure the vibrational sensitivity of the back and buttock to pursue a more exact discussion.

Acknowledgments. This research was supported by the Fellowship Program of Inamori Research Institute for Science, JSPS grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research 21H05071.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors declare no conflicts of interest associated with this manuscript.

References

1. Y. Kurihara, M. Koge, R. Okazaki, and H. Kajimoto, “Large-area Tactile Display using Vibration Transmission of Jammed Particles”, Proceedings of the IEEE Haptics Symposium, pp.313–317, 2014.
2. P. Lemmens, F. Cromptoets, D. Brokken, J. van den Eerenbeemd, and G.-J. de Vries, “A Body-conforming Tactile Jacket to Enrich Movie Viewing”, Proceedings of the IEEE World Haptics Conference, pp.7–12, 2009.
3. K. Shirota, M. Uju, R. Peoros, and, K. Minamizawa, “Liquid-VR- Wetness Sensations for Immersive Virtual Reality Experiences”, Proceedings of the IEEE Asia Haptics Conference, pp.252–255, 2018.
4. K. Kuhara, K. Komazaki, J. Watanabe, and, Y. Tanaka, “Spatiotemporal Perception of Single Overlapped Vibrotactile Stimulation to Multiple Body Locations”, Proceedings of the IEEE World Haptics Conference, pp.162–168, 2023.